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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

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Executive summary

The human-centric prototype evaluation of the XR demonstrators is a key part of THEIA^{XR} to determine the levels to which the commensurable project goals have been achieved. Evaluation is also essential within the development through identifying optimization potentials and design recommendations. Our defined project goals encompass safety, privacy, work performance and quality of work factors. We understand that implementing XR technologies alone is not enough to solve the challenges that come with digitalizing machine operation. Instead, XR interaction must be designed precisely to fit the requirements and expectations. It must provide clear benefits (e.g. operation performance) that must outweigh potential cost (e.g. adaptation, impaired intuitiveness, information overload). Many technical and human factors impact this trade-off and the applicability and performance of the outcomes. Thus, an iterative process that involves the consideration and evaluation of human factors and work performance criteria is important. The first version of this deliverable presents our modular evaluation strategy that we aim to conduct for our developed interaction concepts and technology embedded in interactive demonstrators.

This deliverable is structured as follows: Section 2 gives a brief overview about the XR HMI concepts and prototypes that are expected to be object to evaluation as results of THEIA^{XR}. Section 3 elaborates aim, scope and criteria of the evaluation efforts and discusses their relevance in interaction and work context. Section 4 describes our operationalization of these criteria to be measurable within our project scope. Section 5 describes our planned two-phase evaluation approach and section 6 gives a structured outlook on planned activities to inform the final version, deliverable 3.10.

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1 Introduction

In researching novel ways to connect experienced machine operators with advanced digital technologies and services (e.g.) and even involving them in novel operation scenarios THEIA^{XR} will stress the operators' mental capabilities, expectations and attitudes towards technology. This project started with our conceptual ideas that defined the potential of XR for machine operation. Within the first year, these ideas become elaborated interaction concepts (deliverables 4.4 and 4.8) and technologies (deliverables 3.4, 4.2, 5.3, and 5.5) embedded in digitalized workflows and operation scenarios (deliverable 3.7).

However, we understand that implementing XR technologies alone is not enough to solve the challenges that come with digitalizing machine operation. Instead, XR interaction must be designed precisely to fit the requirements and expectations. It must provide clear benefits (e.g. operation performance) that must outweigh potential cost (e.g. adaptation, impaired intuitiveness, information overload). Many technical and human factors impact this trade-off and the applicability and performance of the outcomes. Thus, an iterative process that involves the consideration and evaluation of human factors and work performance criteria is important. Version 1 of this deliverable presents our modular evaluation strategy that we aim to conduct for our developed interaction concepts and technology embedded in interactive demonstrators.

This deliverable is structured as follows: Section 2 gives a brief overview about the XR HMI concepts and prototypes that are expected to be object to evaluation as results of THEIA^{XR}. Section 3 elaborates aim, scope and criteria of the evaluation efforts and discusses their relevance in interaction and work context. Section 4 describes our operationalization of these criteria to be measurable within our project scope. Section 5 describes our planned two-phase evaluation approach and section 6 gives a structured outlook on planned activities to inform version 2 of this deliverable.

2 Overview about available prototypes

Several approaches on how to utilize XR interaction for machine operation have been developed. Even though many of them are applicable in more than one use case, interaction concepts for each use case comprises of distinct configurations and combinations that meet the specific requirements. The HMI concepts combine several sub-systems of interactive functions based on different information origins or work procedures. Even though these will work simultaneously, our scientific evaluation approach focuses on the performance evaluation of these sub systems. This section provides a short summary of the involved sub-systems and their anticipated role, benefits and costs in machine operation.

2.1 XR-HMI prototype for UC1 (Snow Groomer)

The operation of a snow groomer is becoming more difficult, as constantly more information is available which the operator of the snow groomer has to take care of, whereas the environment around the snow groomer is becoming more difficult to handle (e.g., skiers around the vehicle, environment conditions, etc.). The additional information can nevertheless support the operator in guidance and operation even in bad-view or challenging conditions (weather, etc.). The operation environment contains temperature ranges from -35°C up to 20°C, sun, rain, snow fall, ice rain, fog, wind and darkness which increases the workload to the operator.

One of the key problems in operating a snow groomer is that the human operator has to constantly keep his hands on the controls of the snow groomer and can thus not directly interact with the available data on display-based interfaces. The data presented to the human operator must be suitable, and not be distracting from the task at hand. Additionally, one of the largest problems with operating a snow groomer is that much of the environment around the vehicle is not visible to the human operator or at least not in an acceptable manner.

Figure 1: Key visual of the XR HMI concept for use case 1 (snow groomer)

Situation awareness regarding obstacles and target ground profile are critical factors in snow groomer operation. The XR HMI concept for this use case comprises of different augmenting information presentations that give the operator additional information about the presence and position of obstacles (A), slope profile (B), tool setup (C,D), navigation and area restrictions (B,D) through different forms of augmenting feedback modalities (visual, acoustic and haptic feedback).

2.2 XR-HMI prototype for UC2 (Reachstacker)

In a remote control setup, operators have multiple video screen lacking intuitive depth perception. From the footage, they observe how the container approaches the landing point in truck, another container or cassette and how it settles on its place.

Figure 2: Key visual of the XR HMI concept for use case 2 (reachstacker)

Depth is difficult to perceive through video footage. Supporting the operator to perceive spatial information from the real environment and to stay aware of items not visible in the cameras is a challenge.

Safe operation requires that operators have enough information about surroundings. Since the visibility and feeling of presence (the sounds, vibration and movement of the machine) are not going to be on the same level in remote operation than driving a machine from the cabin, it is very important that the operators feel that they are controlling the machine in a safe and predictable manner and they have enough information about the surroundings. More research on how to provide information to operator about position and surroundings of a machine, height of stack, layout of a block and details of a task is recommended.

The XR HMI concept for this use case comprises of different augmenting information presentations that give the operator additional information about the presence and position of obstacles (A), tool position (B), tool setup (C,D), navigation and area restrictions (B,D) through different forms of augmenting feedback modalities (visual, acoustic and haptic feedback).

2.3 XR-HMI prototype for UC3 (Excavator)

Excavator operators are confronted with an increasing demand for infrastructure and residential building while it's facing a significant lack in skilled labour and technological development, i.e., digitalisation and automation. Higher task load and changing machine functionalities are consequences. Assistance systems, automated machines and construction robotics, model-based workflows and ubiquitous connectivity are the key factors to leverage the productivity in the construction sector, especially in earth-moving machinery. Hence, HMIs are getting complex and thus counter intuitive. Besides operating the machine, operators are facing tasks like handling and manipulating digital models, controlling collaborating machine fleets as well as surveying and documenting the work results. Heterogeneous environmental influences, significant noise and vibration levels and a very busy surrounding with a high potential for accidents typically characterise the working conditions in a construction machine.

Figure 3: Key visual of the XR HMI concept for use case 2 (excavator)

The XR HMI concept for this use case comprises of different augmenting information presentations that give the operator additional information about the presence and position of obstacles (A), tool position (B), tool setup (C,D), navigation and area restrictions (B,C, D) through different forms of augmenting feedback modalities (visual, acoustic and haptic feedback).

3 Evaluation framework

Most of the XR features aim for presenting information closer in the field of view of operators that focus on the environment of the machine. Reducing complexity and actively guiding attention through feedback signals and dynamic and adjustable visual complexity are other approaches that aim to support operators in gaining situational awareness. However, such novel information presentation modalities may turn out to bring more harm than benefits. Known threats to system performance are the use of unfamiliar cues, number of simultaneous signals and signal complexity, that can lead to distraction, high workload and confusion with negative impacts on work performance. A careful design is necessary to utilize the potential of XR technology and to avoid these impairments. THEIA^{XR} Utilizes a two phase evaluation strategy to keep track of these issues from technical, psychological, social and cognitive perspectives.

Elaborating the concepts presented in section 2 and implementing them into interactive demonstrators, reveal design and functional dimensions that must be adjusted to the operators' requirements. Criteria such as interaction performance, usability, intuitiveness, safety, physical and cognitive ergonomics extend the list of requirements for technical products, eventually defining the quality of a human-technology fit. Above all of that, the concept of humane technology is dedicated to aligning technology to human needs rather than exploiting human vulnerabilities. Within the project, the partners will investigate different multimodal UI concepts and rate them with respect to usability, mental load, system-level risk analysis, in the context both of on-vehicle and off-vehicle (tele-operation). Section three describes the scope of the concept evaluation that take place and what evaluation criteria will be focused to empirically demonstrate the performance potential of our XR interaction concepts.

3.1 Scope and aim of evaluation

In researching novel ways to connect experienced machine operators with advanced digital technologies and services (e.g.) and even involving them in novel operation scenarios THEIA^{XR} will stress the operators' mental capabilities, expectations and attitudes towards technology. This project started with our conceptual ideas that defined the potential of XR for machine operation. Within the first year, these ideas become elaborated interaction concepts and technologies embedded in digitalized workflows and operation scenarios.

However, we understand that implementing XR technologies alone is not enough to solve the challenges that come with digitalizing machine operation. Instead, XR interaction must be designed precisely to fit the requirements and expectations. It must provide clear benefits (e.g. operation performance) that must outweigh potential cost (e.g. adaptation, impaired intuitiveness, information overload). Many technical and human factors impact this trade-off and the applicability and performance of the outcomes. Thus, an iterative process that involves the consideration and evaluation of human factors and work performance criteria is important. The first version of this deliverable presents our modular evaluation strategy that we aim to conduct for our developed interaction concepts and technology embedded in interactive demonstrators.

3.2 Evaluation criteria for XR HMI

Industrial use cases are determined through a set of key criteria: productivity, efficiency, and safety. They refer to different states and situations and may interact with each other, creating conflicts of objectives (e.g. productivity vs. safety). HMIs are also regularly evaluated against associated quality criteria. Usability and user experience (UUX), intuitiveness and perceived ease of use are such criteria that are directly related to the HMIs appearance, functionality, and performance. Interaction performance of operators with distinct user interfaces also relate to a set of prominent human factors in interaction and user interface research. Among them are situational awareness, acceptance or workload. Another dimension of criteria is situation related. Different situations require evaluation of different information or the proficient use of different system functions to be effectively and efficiently solved. Thus, reliable measurement of HMI qualities must be performed in the context of a task or situation.

Theia XR is committed to investigate effects of XR HMI approaches regarding the following criteria:

- A. Improved **safety** for operator, vehicle and persons and objects in vicinity (UC1, UC2, UC3): Safety is often referred to be the most important operational criteria and refers to design and functional features that help to prevent accidents, machine abuse and operational errors. The higher the operational safety of a system is the lower the probabilities are these to occur [1][2].
- B. **Usability** (UC1, UC2, UC3): Usability is the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use. Usability refers to the ease with which people can use a product or system to achieve their goals effectively, efficiently, and satisfactorily [3]. It involves assessing how user-friendly and intuitive a product or system is, considering factors such as learnability (how easy it is for users to understand and use the product), efficiency (how quickly users can perform tasks), memorability (how easily users can remember how to use the product over time), error prevention and recovery (how well the product helps users avoid and correct mistakes), and satisfaction (how pleasant and satisfying the user experience is). Usability is essential in design to enhance user experience, increase user adoption, and ultimately improve the success and acceptance of a product or system [4].
- C. **Quality of work** (UC1, UC2, UC3): The concept of quality of work refers to the standard of excellence exhibited in tasks, projects, or output produced by individuals or teams within a professional context [5]. It encompasses various aspects, including accuracy, completeness, effectiveness, efficiency, reliability, and consistency. Quality of work is often evaluated based on how well it meets predefined criteria, standards, or expectations, as well as its overall impact on achieving organizational goals or fulfilling customer needs. Achieving high-quality work involves attention to detail, adherence to standards and best practices, continuous improvement efforts, and a commitment to delivering value to stakeholders. Quality of work is also used to describe a hedonistic quality in work (Quality in work life), focusing more on individual joy and need fulfilment through facilitating work conditions [6].
- D. **Operation performance** (UC2): Machine operation performance refers to the efficiency, effectiveness, and reliability of a machine or automated system in carrying out its intended tasks or functions. It involves assessing various metrics such as speed, accuracy, throughput, uptime, downtime, and energy consumption. High machine operation performance indicates that the machine can complete tasks quickly, accurately, and consistently while minimizing errors, breakdowns, and maintenance needs. Achieving optimal machine operation performance often involves proper maintenance, calibration, and utilization of the machine, as well as continuous monitoring and improvement efforts to enhance productivity and reduce operational costs.
- E. Increasing **performance** in using digital design models (UC3): This is considered a more specific instance of operation performance and can be described similar to criteria D. However, interacting with digital design models require more sophisticated prototypes that allow for visually and effectively manipulate such data with receiving realistic feedback.
- F. Increasing **productivity** (UC2): Productivity refers to the amount of work is conducted by a system. In machine operation criteria such as effectivity and time spend on conducting a task are directly related to the systems overall productivity.
- G. **Situation awareness** (UC1, UC2, UC3): Situation awareness refers to the understanding and perception of the environment and the dynamic elements within it, including events, objects, people, and their interactions [7]. It involves being aware of relevant information, predicting future developments, and making effective decisions based on this understanding. Situation awareness is crucial in various contexts, such as aviation, military operations, healthcare, and emergency

response, where individuals need to monitor and comprehend complex situations rapidly and accurately to respond appropriately. Effective situation awareness relies on factors such as perception, comprehension, projection, and decision-making, as well as the ability to filter and prioritize relevant information amidst distractions or uncertainties [8].

- H. **Acceptance:** Technology acceptance refers to the willingness and readiness of individuals or groups to adopt and use a new technology. It involves understanding the factors that influence users' perceptions and attitudes toward technology adoption, including perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and other social and organizational factors. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and its variations provide frameworks for studying and predicting users' intentions to adopt technology based on these factors. Successful technology acceptance occurs when users perceive the technology as beneficial, easy to use, and compatible with their needs, leading to widespread adoption and utilization of the technology within an organization or society [9].
- I. **Intuitivity:** Intuitivity refers to the fit between a HMI's design and appearance and the users' expectations and mental models. Poor intuitivity can significantly impair operation performance, workload and satisfaction, that will very likely result in poor usability and performance ratings. Intuitivity is sometimes associated to be a part of usability [10].

4 Evaluation method and data assessment

All evaluation criteria listed in section 3 are common metrics in HMI research. Thus, validated measurement tool (e.g. questionnaires and experimental setups) exist for the most of them. However, regarding their origin regarding scientific domain, different approaches to operationalize these criteria exist. Also use-case specific performance measures might require the adoption of general measures and experimental designs. Section 4 provides a list of measures and two general experimental design that we plan to use to evaluate our XR HMI prototypes with different stakeholders.

4.1 Measures

- A. Improved **safety** for operator, vehicle and persons and objects in vicinity (UC1, UC2, UC3): Safety is a system characteristic that can be assessed through elaborated tools and procedures (ISO 12100:2010). However, safety might also express in improved performance (less safety violations or critical situations). Focussing on the operators, other measures exist to determine predictors of safe operation. These can be cognitive states, e.g. situational awareness, attitudes such as safety awareness or adequate behaviour (e.g. regularly checking mirrors).

For our evaluation of operational safety, we plan to include two measures:

A1: The operators' situation awareness regarding potential safety threats (see D), and

A2: The operators' safety-related behaviour (e.g. regularly checking for obstacles in the environment)

- B. **Usability** (UC1, UC2, UC3): Usability is an established measure, and several questionnaires exist. One of this technique is the System Usability Scale, a questionnaire that consists of ten questions. It is a highly cited usability assessment technique. and a very easy scale to administer, massively applied in different domains, showing reliability to distinguishing usable and unusable systems and interfaces both with small and large sample sizes. Other self-reporting usability assessment techniques include the Questionnaire for User Interface Satisfaction (QUIS) [11], developed at the HCI lab at the University of Maryland, the Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) and the Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use scale (PUEU), both developed at IBM [12][13].

For our evaluation of operational safety, we plan to include four measures:

B1: The System Usability Scale [14], and

B2: The usability components of the UEQ+ questionnaire (e.g. efficiency, usefulness, intuitive use, novelty, trust, quality of content, or comprehensibility) [15].

B3: INTUI, a validated 17-item questionnaire that focus intuitivity of a system [16].

B4: Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use scale (PUEU), a validated 14+14-item scale focusing the measurement of usefulness and perceived ease of use [13].

- C. **Quality of Work, Productivity, Operation Performance and Performance in using digital models during machine operation** will be assessed through explicit measures of task performance. These measures can be time on task, and accuracy of execution. Both measures require defined performance standards and tasks. Result will be most valuable if compared to a baseline condition. Task performance measures can differ between use cases and between tasks, as the involved procedures and goals may involve different quality criteria.

For our evaluation of work performance, we plan to include two measures that must be defined in the context of relevant tasks:

C1: Time on Task, and (explicit measures)

C2: Accuracy of task execution (explicit measures)

- D. **Situation Awareness:** SA has been widely considered as an important factor in dynamic decision-making, and several indirect or subjective methods (e.g., physiological measurement, performance measures, self-rating) have been proposed and used in interaction research in human computer and human machine interaction.

For our evaluation of situation awareness, we plan to adapt one measure

D1: SPAM - A query-based SA measurement method. In this method, the operator is presented with queries about the situation while the situation remains present and while the operator performs primary tasks [17].

- E. **Acceptance:** According to the technology acceptance model, acceptance cannot be measured upon initial use. However, it has been shown to rely on precursors such as usefulness, usability, satisfaction (positive UX), ease of use, trust, or perceived risk [18]. We argue to use the measures above to discuss an acceptance tendency towards the evaluated concepts.

4.2 Assessment procedure

The evaluation will encompass user studies that will follow a structured sequence of briefings and control tasks designed to evaluate the XR HMI criteria listed above. Participants will use our interaction prototypes that replicate real-world conditions and cover common operational functions such as manoeuvring, and tool movement. The tasks will be performed in a controlled environment to standardize conditions, including machine type, environmental obstacles, and visual obstructions.

Participants will first complete an orientation session, which will include a briefing on machine controls, safety guidelines, and the specific objectives of each task. Following orientation, participants will perform the predefined machine operation tasks while interaction data is collected via integrated system sensors, standardized and non-standardized questionnaires, and manual observation. Each task session will last approximately 30–60 minutes.

4.3 Experiment Subjects

Each study will recruit a sample of professional off-highway machine operators from the target domain. Participants will have varied levels of experience, from entry-level to expert, to capture a range of interaction performance. All subjects will be screened for recent experience with similar machines to ensure they have baseline familiarity with relevant controls and typical operational challenges. In total, we anticipate recruiting 10–50 participants per experiment, segmented by experience level (novice, intermediate, expert) to allow for comparative analysis across expertise categories. Demographic details, including age, years of professional experience, and machine-specific experience, will be recorded for all participants.

5 Evaluation Procedures

To evaluate our XR HMI concepts through prototypes we plan to conduct two different stages of evaluation. In the first stage we evaluate issues and potential of the HMI concepts with first versions of prototypes and internal stakeholders. This stage aims at identifying cross-use case/industry applicability and scalability of concepts as well as involving expertise from different scientific and industrial areas (engineering, design,). The second phase is focussing end users and evaluates different qualities of the HMI concepts in interactive Trials. This second stage aims at empirically measuring and demonstrating positive impacts of XR interaction on work performance. It further derives qualitative feedback on the perceived benefits and threats of novel interaction concepts and XR interaction in particular.

5.1 Internal evaluation

The THEIA^{XR} consortium covers different industrial and scientific areas. It involved and associated partners bring different perspectives into the project. The development of XR interaction concepts in THEIA^{XR} is also approached from different areas: technical explorations, human-centred requirements and domain characteristics. Use case XR HMI concepts merge all these approaches by introducing a set of functionalities for future machine operation. After consolidating our first version of the XR HMI concepts and their demonstration in singular, interactive prototypes, we are currently evaluating these demos within our project consortium. Thus this evaluation focuses on feedback from professional subject matter experts (SME) that have an understanding on the topic and scope of XR interaction in off-high way machines. Within the project consortium we are able to involve the perspectives of sensor and IT technology, interaction technology, social science, psychology and technology integration. With the internal evaluation we want to critically challenge technical feasibility, work related usefulness, privacy, work experience and implementability.

Besides our regular discussions within the project meetings, we want to conduct a formalized questionnaire to document the various SME assessments. Participants of the internal evaluation study will be introduced into the concept and then test the demonstrator within its limits. Then the SMEs are asked to fill out a short questionnaire. The questionnaire does not ask for demographic data and focusses on constructive feedback.

It gives a brief overview about the presented features (Figure 1, upper part), and asks to rate the potential with regard to our claim to better connect the machine operator with digital information, what is positive and negative about the presented features, and how it can be improved to be more useful and immersive. The questionnaire also provides an abstract cockpit view here subjects can draw remarks and suggestions for improvement. Feedback of all SMEs is collected and assessed data will be summarized into list of feedback items, that will be prioritized in a second review phase. With this internal evaluation we want to make sure that considerations and requirements from all involved domains will be considered halfway to concept completion.

Feedback Questionnaire: Excavator XR-Interaction

The excavator showed several prototypical approaches of XR-Interaction and information presentation to you. These ideas are meant to extend existing interaction functionalities to increase immersion, usability, and accessibility of digital data meant to increase situation awareness, control performance, and process precision.

These ideas have been presented:

A	B	C
A real-time 3D data of surface profile visualization implemented in a 3D machine display.	A customizable screen layout that enables switching between virtual machine model visualization and real camera streams.	An arm-mounted relative position indicator Display

As we continue to improve visualization, functionality, and integration, we would like to ask you to give some feedback about the technologies you have just experienced. Please add your comments to the questions below. Additionally, you can use the drawing space on the back to sketch your ideas and remarks.

A	B	C
1. How do you rate the potential with regard to our claim to better connect the machine operator with digital information?		
2. What did you find positive?		
3. What did you notice negatively?		
4. What needs to be improved to be more useful?		
5. What needs to be improved to be more immersive?		

Please use this space for explanatory sketches.

Thank you for your feedback! This will be considered in our further work.

Figure 4: Questionnaire for the internal evaluation of XR HMI concepts.

5.2 End user evaluation

The internal evaluations that utilize the procedure described in section 5.1. aim at identifying opportunities and deficiencies. In a second phase end user evaluations are conducted to measure actual performance and validate design decisions. These are more complex and require higher level fidelity prototypes that are capable of covering realistic interaction scenarios. Performance evaluation will be mainly based on live experiments that present the XR HMI concepts to machine operators.

To increase efficiency in end user evaluation, it is planned to provide a universal and modular XR HMI experimental design and data analysis procedure. This can then be utilized and altered to prepare and conduct several end user studies to evaluate our demonstrators. The basic procedure, common in laboratory and field studies in the area of human-machine interaction covers the following steps: (1) Briefing, (2) Pre-Test Questionnaire, (3) Presenting the stimulus/Subjects convey tasks using the HMI artefact, (4) Post-test questionnaire, and (5) data analysis. An outline of the content and scope of each step is presented below. Questionnaires and data analysis will be realized in software such as SoSci Survey (ref.) and r (ref.).

SoSci Survey is a web application for creating online questionnaires. The software is offered by SoSci Survey GmbH as a cloud service and software license. The software comprises 30 different question types with various display options. In addition, individual presentations and research designs can be implemented using various techniques (design customization, HTML/CSS, JavaScript, PHP) [19].

R is a free programming language for statistical calculations and graphics. R is currently available on the most important platforms; the environment is also explicitly referred to as R by the developers. R is considered a standard language for statistical problems in both business and science. Numerous packages available online contain additional functions for analysing data with regard to questions from different specialist areas; further custom functions can be created. The language offers interfaces to other programming languages

and options for integration into various software. It is written primarily in C, Fortran, and R itself. Precompiled executables are provided for various operating systems. As an interpreted language, R has a native command line interface. Moreover, multiple third-party graphical user interfaces are available, such as RStudio, and Jupyter [20]. As we are not expecting complex statistical procedures to be necessary we propose the use of Jamovi, a free to use application for R-based data analysis that offers the advantage of a reduced function range and an easy to use interface. [20].

Predefined modules that will be created to be utilized in end user evaluations of XR HMI concepts are described in Table 1. If several sub-functions of the XR-HMI concepts have to be tested separately, this procedure will be used several times.

Using prototypes to evaluate performance, usability or user experience can be difficult. Impaired functionality due to the lower level of fidelity (e.g. loading times, delay, missing feedback, asynchrony cues) or visible limits in function range or unnatural system behaviour (static machine states, unrealistic environment, dead buttons) will impair the subjects' perception of the interface and he might not consider this offset when answering the questions. Therefore, it is important to provide an as much realistic and flawless presentation of HMI functions as possible. To keep complexity in the creation of the prototypes or demonstrator within reasonable limits it will be better to drastically limit scope and exclude irrelevant cues completely.

	Step of evaluation procedure	Description	Template-tool
1	Briefing	Subjects will be informed about the scope of the evaluation study and receive information about the functionalities of the XR HMI and the tasks they have to conduct during the experiment.	Text-file, SoSci Survey text block
2	Pre-test questionnaire	This questionnaire assesses demographic data (e.g. age, domain specific experience with machine operation, experience with certain technologies, and affinity for technology interaction(ATI)) that help to discuss findings of the live experiment.	SoSci Survey question blocks
3	Stimuli/Live experiment	Subjects are asked to interact with the HMI demonstrator in a free exploration, situation assessment, or control task. As demonstrators are often limited in functional range, these interaction parts will be guided through instructions. Defining the structure and tasks that will be given to the subjects depends on the capabilities of the demonstrator. Behaviour of subjects will be observed and documented in free form. Explicit performance measures (e.g., time on task, accuracy of task results) will be measured and documented in this step as well. To increase expressiveness of measures in step 4, a within-subject design with two conditions (baseline, design A or design A, design B) is recommended.	Text-file, SoSci Survey comment block
4	Post-test questionnaire	This questionnaire assesses the subjects' perception, attitudes and experience in retrospectively. Wherever possible, validated questionnaires will be used (e.g. UEQ+, SUS, SPAM). As UEQ+ and SUS assess an overall reflection of the previous experience, we propose to	SoSci Survey question blocks

		use several instances of these questionnaire referring to certain sub-functions and designs of the features embedded in the demonstrator. More specialized and specific feedback interests will be covered with self-designed Likert-scales, and a semi-structured interview.	
5	Data analysis	Qualitative interview (observations, answers in the interview) will be collected in a structured list. For qualitative data that were assessed with Likert-scales for demographic and other topics, and within the used questionnaires, mean values will be calculated. Correlations between scores will be checked but low statistical power is expected due to the rather small amount of subjects (N between 10 and 20). However, demographic data such as age, prior experience, affinity) will be considered in discussing the findings.	Excel sheet for data transformation, Jamovi file for mean calculation and correlation tests

Table 1: Evaluation procedure for the end-user evaluation

6 Further activities

The evaluation agenda and structure is set to assess important feedback for design refinement (phase one) and benefit/cost estimation of our novel HMI functionalities (phase two). The internal evaluation is currently running and will be reiterated throughout the whole development phase (est. 06/2025). Preparation of end-user evaluation has already started with pre-test taking place during 2024. Final end-user studies will be conducted in 2025.

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